

Constant amplitude fatigue limit of shear bond with headed studs

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ABSTRACT

The highway road network currently lists a large number of bridges that need to be replaced. Composite steel structures are frequently used for this purpose. The composite joints are usually designed with welded headed studs.

Experimental investigations to derive fatigue limits at a high number of loadcycles for headed studs are currently lacking. High load amplitudes lead to a locally damaged concrete in the area of the headed stud base. Due to the continuous expansion of the damaged area, the longitudinal shear forces at the foot of the headed studs are redistributed to the shaft, causing additional bending stresses at the foot. The notch at the foot is now stressed not only by shear but also by bending stresses. The research objective is the derivation of a fatigue limit at which concrete degradation at the foot can be rejected. To investigate this fatigue limit, 3 push-out-tests with decreasing shear force amplitudes were performed. Strain gauges on a lead ring were used to record the continuous concrete degradation at the headed stud foot. After test execution, the surrounding concrete was separated from the steel and visually inspected for fatigue damages.

Keywords: Composite Steel Structures, Headed Studs, Fatigue & Fracture

1 INTRODUCTION AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

In bridge construction, the transverse support structure is approximately at a distance of 4 m (*Fig. 1*). The number of loadcycles for the fatigue design in the transverse direction must therefore be based on the number of axis rather than on the number of trucks. This results in approx. $N \approx 8 \times 10^8$ to 10×10^8 loadcycles over the service life (1, 2). The fatigue strength for shear loading of headed studs is currently described by a linear fatigue strength curve (Miner elementary) with a constant inclination $m = 8$ and the characteristic 2-Mio value $\Delta\tau_c = 90$ MPa. The reason for this lies in the previously postulated assumption that there is no constant amplitude fatigue limit (CAFL) for concrete, consequently an unexplored CAFL remains unconsidered.

Fig. 1. a) Langenfelder Brücke (A7, Hamburg, Germany); b) Variant of the cantilever beam connection

Other fatigue strength curves are also known in the international technical literature (3, 4). The design concept for fatigue of headed studs was initially developed by Roik and Hanswille around the 1990s (5, 6). To substantiate the characteristic fatigue strength curve, numerous test series of cyclic displacement and force-controlled push-out-tests were analysed until the headed studs broke. In tests, the cracks at the base of the dowels usually occur much earlier than the fracture, which can be seen in the fracture pattern, for example, by means of the snap lines (7–12). In addition, the significant influence of the level of maximum loads must be taken into account. Due to the decoupling of the ultimate limit state and the fatigue limit state, the contradiction arises for the composite connection that the full static load-bearing capacity is assumed up to the point of fatigue fracture. Doubts were expressed early on about the full static residual load-bearing capacity of the headed studs after cyclic loading and Oehlers observed a linear relationship between the number of loadcycles resisted and the static residual load-bearing capacity (13). This is currently taken into account by limiting the characteristic longitudinal shear force per anchor to 60% of the design value of the headed studs load-bearing capacity (11). On the basis of tests, Mensinger (14) and Leffer (15) confirmed that the crack growth phase takes up a considerable part of the service life. The observed number of loadcycles did not correspond to those calculated on the basis of the nominal stress concept in Eurocode 4 with the linear damage accumulation hypothesis according to Palmgren-Miner, partly also with results on the uncertain side. The influence of the stresses of the steel flange is overestimated and the influence of the direct dowel stress is underestimated, especially in the interaction analysis in the area of internal columns (8, 16). Based on this and their own research, Hanswille, Porsch and Üstündag drew a comprehensive picture of the fatigue behaviour of headed studs (9, 17). Fig. 2 shows the 4 phases of the decrease in the static residual load-bearing capacity over the service life. In the first 10 to 30 % of the related service life (phase I), the related static residual load-bearing capacity drops slightly, followed by a partly disproportionate decrease (phase II), depending on the relative maximum load level. In phase III, the decrease then reduces with an approximately linear progression. Finally, the residual load-bearing capacity decreases disproportionately and the test specimen fails at the level of the maximum load.

Fig. 2. Decrease in residual static load-bearing capacity over the service life (9)

The deformations of the composite joint are divided into an elastic and a plastic part. The first cyclic load causes localised destruction of the concrete in the area of the dowel base. Due to the steady increase in plastic slip, the longitudinal shear forces - initially directed towards the dowel base and later slightly upwards also towards the shank - are additionally redistributed in the stud shaft at higher load levels. According to the interpretation in (17), lower maximum loads cause an increase in

deformation over the service life due to the widened fatigue fracture and forced fracture surfaces within the flange material. At high maximum loads, the fracture surfaces tend to occur within the shaft. These different failure mechanisms have not been finally explained yet.

The fatigue analysis for headed studs in bridge construction is often difficult because in most cases the exact load collectives are not known. If all stress differences are below a scientifically substantiated CAFL, the complexity is significantly reduced and precise knowledge of a load collective is no longer necessary. From the considerations of Mensinger (14) for $d = 22$ mm dowels, derived from the evaluation of service load tests to check the Miner rule, a CAFL of $\Delta\tau_d = 78.9$ MPa for $d = 22$ mm can be indirectly derived. Feldmann and Gesella addressed the problem of crack propagation at the base of the dowel in several experiments in (18). In tests, the slip between the concrete slab and the steel flange increases over the service life. However, this damage in the composite joint did not occur with slip widths of less than 0.1 mm (18, 19). To assess the presence of CAFL, a value of 0.1 mm is therefore specified for the slip width, below which no crack growth occurs. From this, a CAFL of $\Delta\tau_{th} = 57.9$ MPa can be derived for dowels $d = 22$ mm. The results of Porsch (20) indicate a much smaller value (0.01 to 0.02 mm). In the USA, numerous fatigue tests were carried out on composite beams and push-out-test specimens with headed studs. The fatigue strength curve of the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) (3) for shear loading of headed studs is slightly below Eurocode 4 (11, 21) (Fig. 3). However, it defines a CAFL at design level at 3.5 ksi (24 MPa). The mean value of the specified distribution is 45 MPa, see (4).

With regard to the fatigue strength under shear loading of headed studs, numerous test results are available that prove the validity of a very flat Wöhler curve with $m = 8$. The phenomena at very high maximum loads are complex due to localised concrete degradation, so that in (11), as in (22), a limitation of the maximum load to 60% of the headed stud load-bearing capacity is required, which at the same time also takes into account the otherwise reduced residual static load-bearing capacity in the event of previous fatigue loading. The existence and distribution function of a CAFL, which is of great importance for low loads, especially in road bridge construction with many hundreds of millions of loadcycles, has not been clarified.

Fig. 3. S-N-Curve

The available data on fatigue tests with headed studs (5, 9, 14, 15, 20, 23–25) were recorded and three of our own tests were added and analysed. Only tests relevant for composite bridge construction with certain materials ($35 < f_{ck} < 60$ MPa) and maximum loads $< 60\%$ of the dowel load-bearing capacity were included (Fig. 3).

The results of this pre-assessment allow the following interpretation, whereby the database in the very high cycle region ($N \geq 5 \times 10^6$) must be expanded for validation:

- The current fatigue strength curve ($m=8$) stored in Eurocode 4 adequately represents the underlying test data in the fatigue strength range.
- The fatigue strength curve of the AASHTO (3) is slightly lower than that of the Eurocode. It already defines a CAFL or more precisely a fatigue threshold value, but this seems very conservative, which makes fatigue design uneconomical.
- The tests by Ovuoba/Prinz (24) do not justify a CAFL, as they were already cancelled before they reached the quantile values of the fatigue strength curve according to Eurocode 4.

2 FATIGUE TESTS TU BERLIN

2.1 Test specimens

Possibilities for verifying the model of local shear force transmission by measurement were examined by several tests at the TU Berlin (Fig. 4). The aim of these investigations is to measure the main stresses that are very concentrated locally at the base of the stud at service load level. The difficulty here is that the stresses of interest in the concrete at the base of the dowel are not significantly disturbed by the installation parts that are embedded in the concrete. Different variants were therefore investigated in which strain gauges can be placed in the concrete without disturbing the concrete structure.

Simultaneous additional knowledge about the behaviour of the composite joint in the very high cycle region was to be gained by reducing the stress test-by-test. Therefore three push-out-tests were carried out under fatigue loading according to (21).

Fig. 4. Dimensions of a Push-Out-test specimen in mm (DIN EN 1994-1-1 Attachment B)

The concrete mix used was designed in-house. The following boundary conditions had to be taken into account when creating it:

- Due to the measuring technology to be installed in the concrete structure and the resulting space limitations at the dowel base (*Table 3*), the maximum grain size could not be larger than $D = 8$ mm.
- A self-compacting concrete (SCC) was designed, because it was not possible to subsequently compact the fresh concrete after concreting due to the very sensitive measuring elements.
- The minimum concrete quality for bridge construction is C35/45 due to the exposition class. In order to obtain realistic and safe test results, the concrete quality C35/45 should be achieved, but not significantly higher than that.

The following recipe has resulted from these requirements:

Table 1. Concrete mix design

	Weight		Volume	
CEM II 32,5:	300,0	[kg]	100,0	[l]
Microsilica:	250,0	[kg]	113,6	[l]
Water:	224,0	[kg]	224,0	[l]
Aggregates 0/2:	804,2	[kg]	309,3	[l]
Aggregates 2/8:	658,0	[kg]	253,1	[l]
Concrete liqefier:	2,5	[%]		

Additionally the water content in per cent by mass was 2.64% for aggregate 0/2 and 1.42% for 2/8. The fresh concrete properties of this concrete fulfil the requirements for a SCC with a spreading dimension of 900 mm (> 700 mm). Average hardened concrete properties (28 days) were achieved according to *Table 2*. With these hardened concrete properties, the selected concrete mix design can be assigned to concrete grade C35/45 in accordance with DIN EN 206 (26).

Table 2. Hardened concrete properties

Cube compressive strength:	$f_{ck, cube}$	=	46,1	[MPa]
Cylindrical compressive strength:	$f_{ck, zyl}$	=	48,5	[MPa]
Splitting tensile strength:	f_{ctm}	=	3,20	[MPa]
Modulus of elasticity:	E_{cm}	=	26670	[MPa]

Due to its very dense structure, SCC has the property of easily becoming high strengths. To counteract this tendency, a high amount of microsilica was used. In standardised concrete, the use of microsilica has other objectives and is limited due to its strength-reducing properties. Here, however, a low-strength SCC could only be achieved by this procedure and thus fulfils the research purpose.

The concreting was carried out lying down. The left side was concreted first and the right side 12 days later. This procedure was chosen to avoid cutting the steel girder vertically and welding it back together later. The development of the concrete properties takes place mainly in the first few days. Later, the concrete properties then asymptotically approach a limit value. The resulting differences in the properties, due to the time-shifted concreting, are only in the range of a normal scattering. It turned out that this procedure had no significant influence on the test results.

2.2 Measuring technology

During the tests, in addition to recording the number of loadcycles and the force and displacement values of the testing machine, a continuous measurement of the slip in the composite joint was recorded. Four inductive displacement sensors (IDS) were used for slip measurement and installed at the lower end of the composite joint. Four different variants were used to measure the concrete strain

in the concrete structure itself (Table 3). Reinforcing steel was used as the carrier material for the strain gauges in two variants and lead or a cement ring in other variants.

Table 3. Variants for strain measurement in concrete

Variant 1	Variant 2	Variant 3	Variant 4
Strain gauges on straight reinforcing steel \varnothing 6mm	Strain gauges on lead strip ($E_{cm} \approx E_{Pb}$)	Strain gauge on cement ring (not executed)	Strain gauges on reinforcement ring

This showed that variants 1 and 2 performed best in terms of manufacturability and ease of handling during installation. The best quality measurement results were obtained with variant 2. Variant 3 was not realised, as it was not possible to develop a mix design for the concrete ring with approximately the same concrete properties as usual for a C35/45. Variant 4 proved to be particularly unsuitable for applying strain gauges, which is why the authors do not always consider the recorded results from this variant to be plausible. All strain gauges were only protected from the alkaline environment of the concrete by a protective coating in order to minimise further disruption to the concrete structure.

2.3 Test execution

After installation in the testing machine, the tests were first run step by step up to their maximum load and then loaded with a frequency of 7.5 to 10 Hz. After 10,000 loadcycles, one measuring cycle was applied. To do this, the frequency was reduced to 0.1 Hz for a loadcycle, whereby the load was held for 10 seconds at both the maximum and minimum load.

The tests were exposed to a fatigue load until failure of a composite joint could be determined. The three tests were each carried out with different stress amplitudes, starting with the highest stress amplitude. In general, the test procedure is designed as a single-stage collective, corresponding to a Wöhler test. However, if no significant composite joint damage (slip) was detected after reaching the loadcycle median according to Eurocode 4, the stress amplitude was increased (two-stage collective). This test procedure was chosen because a single-stage load at the level of a low stress amplitude leads inevitably to very long test durations. On the other hand, the linear damage hypothesis and the assumption of the known fatigue strength curve (EC4) can be used to determine by calculation whether predamage has already occurred under the previous stress amplitudes.

3 ANALYSIS OF THE TEST RESULTS

3.1 Service life

Tests V-DSK_I and V-DSK_II (X in Fig. 3) were subjected to cyclic loading until one composite joint failed. The failure criteria were either a strong increase in slip or a complete failure (forced or residual fracture) of the composite joint.

With V-DSK_III (O in Fig. 3), no significant damage could be detected in the composite joint after 2.62×10^7 loadcycles. The stress range was therefore increased and the test was cancelled after a further 2.67×10^7 loadcycles. For the second stress range alone, a number of loadcycles was achieved that is above the fatigue strength curve of the EC4 (50% quantile). It can therefore be assumed that the first amplitude block did not lead to any effective pre-damage or partial damage.

Table 4. Service life

test:	V-DSK_I	V-DSK_II	V-DSK_III
max. stress [MPa]:	116	161	161
min. stress [MPa]:	2	65	80 + 65
double amplitude [MPa]:	114	96	81 + 96
loadcycles [-]:	3.450.000 (failure)	10.960.000 (failure)	26.242.000 + 26.721.000 (run out)

3.2 Slip in the composite joint

With V-DSK_I, all 4 headed studs on the right-hand side of the test were completely disconnected. The fatigue crack spread into the beam flange below the weld collar. The linear expansion of the fatigue cracks took up approx. 85% of the stud diameter.

V-DSK_II, on the other hand, was cancelled when disproportionate slip movement became noticeable in the left composite joint. When the studs were later exposed, stud cracks were found in the left-hand composite joint, whereas no cracks were visible in the right-hand composite joint. From this it can be concluded that the slip that has occurred up to that point is solely due to the degradation of the concrete at the base of the dowel. The stud cracks seem to appear at a later stage. The V-DSK_III test did not show any stud cracks.

Table 5. Slip

Value range of the Y-axes: 0 to 1.2 [mm] ; Value range of the X-axes depending on the number of loadcycles achieved

3.3 Concrete strain and damage at the stud base

The concrete strain within the concrete structure were recorded in the area close to the stud bases. Therefore different measurement concepts according to section 2.2 were used. If the strains of the different measurement concepts are compared with each other, it can be seen that the strains are significantly lower when steel is used as the carrier material instead of lead. This clearly shows the expected reinforcing effect of steel (higher modulus of elasticity) as a carrier material for strain gauges. With a modulus of elasticity of approx. 20,000 MPa, lead is of a similar or even lower order of magnitude than the concrete used. A reinforcing effect is not possible. The lead ring is "pulled" by the concrete while lying in the bond, whereby more meaningful results for the concrete strain are achieved than with conventional measurement concepts.

Table 6. Concrete strain

test:	V-DSK_I	V-DSK_II
strain gauge carrier (lead)		
Strain gauge carrier (reinforcement straight)		no measurement results
Strain gauge carrier (reinforcement ring)	no measurement results	

Value range of the Y-axes: 0 to 550 [$\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$] ; Value range of the X-axes depending on the number of loadcycles achieved

After the end of the tests, the concrete surrounding the headed studs was exposed by a core drill. These concrete cylinders were cut open so that the concrete damage at the base of the studs could then be inspected (Table 7). It can be shown that with V-DSK_I with low maximum load and maximum double amplitude, has relatively large concrete destruction at the base. At the end of the test, the removed material was found as concrete dust underneath the composite joint. V-DSK_II (higher maximum load with lower double amplitude) showed significantly lower, but in some cases still substantial, concrete abrasion. With V-DSK_III (same maximum load with lower double amplitude), however, no more concrete destruction could be detected; the contour of the weld collar on the dowel base was still recognisable after the end of the test.

Table 7. Concrete damage at the stud base

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Due to the increasing use of composite construction methods in bridge building, there is a considerable need for research into the long-term behaviour of the composite joint. In particular, the focus is on the behaviour of the headed studs used for the connection under fatigue loads. Existing research results relevant to bridge construction were compiled and compared with the fatigue strength curve in Eurocode 4.

The department of "Conceptual and Structural Design – Steel Construction" at TU Berlin has developed a research project together with TU Munich based on the identified and presented needs. One focus of this project is the scientific justification for a constant amplitude fatigue limit (CAFL). The fatigue tests previous to the research programme were presented here.

A total of three tests with low load amplitudes were evaluated and analysed according to their service life and damage in the composite joint. This was done on the one hand by analysing the slip behaviour, but also by examining the stud base and the surrounding concrete. In addition, a measurement concept was developed that allows concrete strains within the concrete structure to be measured in a more meaningful way.

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